

Recursive Singularity – 8T

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August 11, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T and in particular a situation in which the manifold collapses, it is possible to predict that compressed manifolds will get flattened. That means an expansion or singularity. The reason for such a phenomena is that the compressed manifold is still varying, and the moment a curvature will appear on the compressed manifold, will lead to an acceleration from it.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \tag{1.44}$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Suppose the manifold collapses inward, so that the new equation is:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46.B)$$

Positive time invariant acceleration toward areas of negative curvature, and suppose that this process yielded a compressed manifold of maximal density. Now that the manifold is compressed to maximal density, it is still part of the universe packet, and if for any moment in time, a positive curvature will appear on it, it will again revert to equation (1.46). Meaning that a positive curvature, assuming extremum, will lead to an acceleration from it as a result. Since that manifold is compressed and dense to the maximum this acceleration can be regarded as a moment in which the density of the manifold is going via a phase change. From a compressed manifold to an expanded manifold. That is in other words, the moment of singularity. The pressure exerted on the compressed manifold is the pressure given by the entire universe packet, which lead as you may imagine to radically rapid expansion. This was previously mentioned in the 8T thesis.

The main point that was not mentioned in the thesis is the following: Compressed manifolds will eventually experience singularity, but expanded manifolds will not experience singularity more than once, if they are not to collapse. If a manifold is somewhat stubborn and "wants" to collapse to a compressed state, the manifold packet will eventually flatten this stubborn manifold to an expanded manifold. Even if the universe collapses to a compressed manifold, it will experience an additional flattening in his future, this will happen in the moment of a net curvature of certain magnitude will appear. Thus, we reach an interesting conclusion, those universes that "decide" to collapse inward will experience recursive singularities, or that the same universe can experience more than one singularity. That is because it is part of the packet given by the main equation of the 8T and supported by the primordial coupling series.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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